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SECTION 1: INTRODUCTION

Dealing with the exploitation plan, I already provided an exploitation strategy in the initial project documentation. The main steps of the strategy are shown in table 1.

Table 1: Exploitation strategy

Action	Target
1) Networking and Dissemination; plus special sessions organization in Conferences in Conferences and Expositions (eg. Turbo Expo)	BH, Siemens, Capstone, Ansaldo, Solar Turbines, OPRA, Valmet, ETN, BIOPLAT cluster, EUBCE, Bioenergy clusters and associations
2) Guidelines on how to design GTCLC plants	Valmet, Babcock Wilcox, Aldor Topsoe, Chalmers University, Huazhong University of Science and Technology, Legislators, Civil Associations
3) Exploitation plan	Partners consortium
4) First prototype realized during Horizon Europe Project	European Union
5) Patent development	EU IP Office (EPO)
6) Final product production and commercialization	Partners consortium
7) Product promotion and marketing	Combined power plants and Bioenergy plants owners and operators in the national Electricity markets (ENEL, Sorigenia, Endesa, Iberdrola, Acciona, Yello, Greenpeace Energy, Entega, NaturStrom, Polarstern, Enercity etc.)

The first step will be Networking, to build up a consortium of main stakeholders (industries, research institutes, energy companies), then based on the guidelines developed in this project and on the Exploitation plan a new Horizon Europe project will be proposed. This will bring to the realization of a prototype GTCLC plant, the filing of patents and gradually to the commercialization of the mature technology. Regarding IPR, there is a specific unit at CSIC in charge of managing the exploitation and dissemination of results as well as IPR issues: Vicepresidencia Adjunta de Transferencia del Conocimiento.

At the end of the project we can say that the analysis and experimental campaign performed at the Instituto de Carboquímica have basically shown that the technology is feasible and a pressurized chemical looping plant can be coupled already to a microgras turbine. Then the plant will need still to be scaled up.

We can see in the following figures some examples of pressurized chemical looping plants. In figure 1 we can see the PFIR (Plug Flow Internally Recirculated) reactor, the pilot is under development in Canada.

Figure 1: Schematic of PFIR geometry. A) 3-dimensional view B) Top-down view C) Side view of stage transition [1]

Figure 2: Simplified scheme of the ICR design (left), and the ICR unit under operation inside the shell (right) [1]

The Internally Recirculated Reactor developed at NTNU and SINTEF is a laboratory scale reactor of the thermal power equal to 5 kW_{th}. For pressurized chemical looping also the switch gas concept developed by Cloete can be of great interest [2-5]

Figure 3: Pressurized Chemical Looping Plant at the University of Kentucky [6]

Both the plants proposed by Kentucky University and Korea Institute of Energy Research & KEPCO are based on the connected dual fluidized bed reactors configuration. Even though some pressurized chemical looping plants have been produced at the pilot scale no plant has been connected to a microgas turbine at the moment.

Figure 4: (a) Schematic and (b) 3D-view of the pressurized two interconnected fluidized bed system developed by Korea Institute of Energy Research & KEPCO [7]

Problems with the connection to a microgas turbine can be represented by: small particles of oxygen carrier can be entrained in the gas expanding in the turbine causing damage to the turbine blades; pressure fluctuations at the exit of the air reactor; pressure losses inside the fluidized beds which can be higher respect to the pressure loss of a conventional gas turbine combustor. The entraining of particulate matter in fluidized beds is obviously proportional to the attrition process which is responsible to the decrease of the diameter of the particles which facilitates their entrainment.

For the above-mentioned reasons three future actions seem to be propaedeutic to the realization of a pilot plant:

1. A technoeconomic analysis on the coupling of a small scale chemical looping plant to a micro-gasturbine.
2. A digital twin of the plant capable of proposing some control logic to maintain a constant pressure at the inlet of the gas turbine;
3. An estimate of the startup costs of a laboratory which could showcase the technology on small 3D-printed reactors (also using the microchannel technology if applicable).

SECTION 2: LABORATORY START UP PACKAGE PROPOSAL AND NEGOTIATION

For what has been said above it seems of great interest to evaluate the startup costs of a laboratory showcasing the GTCLC-NEG technology. This is a key step to help the Marie Curie Fellow to see the fruits of the pursued research and also to build on these and propose new projects to promote his career. With regard to laboratory startup costs and laboratory design there are no definitive guidelines.

Stanford guidelines on laboratory design focus more on safety aspects and buildings requirements [8]. Other documents provide support on how to negotiate startup packages with Universities during hiring. And interesting document is the document about “Negotiating Your Startup Package” developed by the Office of Career & Professional Development [9]. In this document we see that the negotiation process for a startup package has to deal with both: startup funds and space. For this reason it appears of paramount importance to arrive at the interview data with a clear idea of what would be the costs of setting up a new lab in the university. Typically startup packages costs can be divided in 4 categories:

- Reagents

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- Equipment (some of the equipment could be shared with colleagues);
- Staff cost (which can be: student, PhD or postdoc);

Other important aspects are:

- how long will the funds last (3years, 5 years, for example);
- a clear idea of the annual amount which will be needed;
- agreement on the possibility to cancel startup funds in case of winning some funds already.

The newly hired professor or researcher can also interact with the hiring institution to ask support on the following aspects:

- Administrative/clerical support – grant writing support, other writing support, teaching prep, dealing with new hires
- Students/postdocs funded by departmental training grants
- Core facilities and shared research equipment/resources
- Office space, support, photocopying
- Computers and software
- Travel support
- Submission and publication fees (can be \$3000+ per year).

Dealing with laboratory space the important aspects to check are the following:

- Check electricity and other expenses;
- Check the renovation needed;
- Try to get the space agreement written into the official offer.
- If possible try to see the space which is reserved to you in person.

The equipment list is then a key aspect too:

- It can be required already at the time of the final interview;
- It is suggested so to prepare an excel file with a list of equipment also through borrowing other candidates' lists;
- from the list a summary of 1 page has to be produced and shared with the hiring commission (items can be lumped into the following definitions: "Consumables" and "Small Equipment").
- List high-cost items explicitly within your budget summary: you may be asked why these are important, what alternatives (if any), and whether you can share with another investigator.

To be prepared for future interviews and also future projects applications I have prepared my equipment list, which is proposed in table 2.

Table 2: Tentative Equipment list

Item	Cost (€)
3D printed packed bed reactor	10,000
PC	1,000
3D printed microgt	15,000
Injectors	10,000
Gas analysis	50,000
Gas control, flowmeters, piping and valves	10,000
Bench DAQ and automation	20,000
Total	116,000

The equipment consists of a microchannel reactor for pressurized chemical looping to be realized with 3D printing plus a microturbine scale down model which is also to be realized by 3D printing. The idea (which I think it is highly original) it is to show case the GTCLC-NEG plant on a lab scale to students and researchers. The turbine design procedure is taken from a work of the University of Sussex [10]. In figure 5 we show the micro-gasturbine blades.

Figure 5: Example of 3D printed turbine blades [10]

The gas analysis system is comparable to what is used also at the Instituto de Carboquímica, mainly based on Siemens Technology).

SECTION 3: NEGOTIATION STEPS

Here we propose the steps and the strategy to negotiate a permanent position on universities or research institutes which is a key step to see the final fruits of the Marie Curie experience to be completely realized.

Step 1: Receive the job offer; respond intelligently.

- Express enthusiasm
- If they don't offer a printed initial offer, then ask for the basics in writing/email.

Possible responses:

“Well, this is great news. I felt there was a great potential fit when I was on campus and I'm thrilled to receive this offer.”

“It would be really helpful if I could see everything that you've just described in writing -- would it be possible for you to send me the basics of what you just offered in an email?”

- This will give you time to consider the offer carefully and prepare before having a real negotiation discussion. Your goal is to respond only after having time to prioritize your requests. You cannot prioritize effectively during this initial conversation!

–Never tip your hand about individual items or overall offer during the initial offer conversation!

–Do not commit to anything.

–If it's clear that something important is missing, don't mention it yet.

Step 2: Decide if you can succeed in that department. Decide if you MIGHT accept the offer. If so, plan to negotiate.

- The negotiation process is a detailed conversation about how you will succeed.
- Negotiating is important, to ensure that both sides have thought through what you need to succeed.
- “As a rule of thumb you can expect to win roughly four important points of negotiation in your final offer.”

Step 3: Re-evaluate and prioritize your negotiation requests.

Prepare private list:

- Make a prioritized list of what you want that is not provided in the offer.
- Re-evaluate your list of the deal-breakers without which you will fail

Prepare public list:

- Provide a 1-page summary (see “Equipment list”, above)
- If asked to provide a detailed start-up lab budget then “the more detailed the budget, the more credible”.

This is particularly true if you are asking for an amount very close to or more than what the department can likely offer you.

Step 4: Begin negotiating.

a. Start out with a positive and enthusiastic comment.

Possible approach:

First of all, I wanted to say again how thrilled I am to have received this offer...

b. Provide an overview of your requests and ask about how to proceed.

Possible approaches:

...I do have a number of questions. These questions run the gamut from salary issues, to whether or

not my husband will find a job there, to how I will access necessary equipment...

-OR-

...I've outlined four main points to discuss with you about the items presented in the email you sent to

me.

...Is this a good time to discuss these or would you prefer to do it later or perhaps by email?

c. Make and defend your first request.

Possible approach:

...As we discussed previously, I cannot even begin my research program without that microscope, which the department does not currently own. The total cost of that item alone is going to exceed \$200,000 which is half of the overall start up package offered. Purchasing it from my startup funds would compromise my ability to hire and retain the necessary research staff. I don't see how I can succeed if I have to purchase it from my startup funds...so I'm wondering if there is any way that item could be covered by other funds?

Note:

By email, strategic delays are built in. Even if you are having a discussion on the phone, remember that you can ask to stop and continue later.

Possible approach:

...Well, I feel like we're at a point where I need to back up and look at everything we've discussed. I'm encouraged by the progress we've made so far. Can we agree to move onto the next points later?

d. When at a stopping point, review progress and commitments, find out and/or agree on what happens next; always express appreciation.

Possible approach:

...I really appreciate your flexibility on these three items and I'm aware of how much effort it takes to request an approval for moving me to a salary step 2. I feel like we've made a lot of progress already, and I'm looking forward to the possibility of finishing this up. I will re-calculate my reagent budget as you requested and get back to you by tomorrow. What happens from here, on your end?

Step 5: Continue making requests and negotiating until finished.

Always ask for final agreement in writing.

We have heard stories from junior faculty who had agreed to items in the offer in conversation, but once they arrived the space was different; or later on the chair changed and they were pushed to a different research/clinical/teaching balance. Getting the offer in writing will help you defend the offer in these situations.

Principles to follow throughout the process:

- “Approach [the negotiation] as a partnership” (remember, this person also wants to see you succeed)
- Always re-open and close each step with appreciation and enthusiasm.
- Negotiate with integrity.
- –This is not an ego trip -- give on some points.
- –Balance satisfaction with relationship issues.
- Be sure that points are documented in writing (email or letter) at every stage of the process.
- Avoid miscommunication when negotiating
 - Keep detailed notes of each conversation
 - Follow up each conversation with an email summarizing the agreed-upon points
 - Suggest win-win’s.

Possible approach:

...I’m aware that John Smith and Carol Jones and several others would also benefit from access to this microscope. If you could help find departmental funds to purchase it, I will maintain it and schedule it.

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